

Self-efficacy Questionnaire

Mark your level of agreement with the following statements:

- 1: totally disagree
- 2: disagree
- 3: neither agree nor disagree
- 4: agree
- 5: totally agree

ID	Questionnaire Items
TER-SE1	I consider that I have the necessary skills to use robotics in the classroom.
TER-SE2	I am sure that I can involve my students to participate in educational robotics projects.
TER-SE3	I am sure that I can help my students when they have difficulties with educational robotics.
TER-SE4	I feel capable of teaching science-related content to my students through educational robots.
TER-SE5	I have enough knowledge of educational robotics to integrate it into the teaching-learning process.
TER-SE6	I have sufficient knowledge of computational thinking regarding the development of robotics activities in educational contexts.